

NODES – Nord Ovest Digitale e Sostenibile

FLAGSHIP PROJECT CIRIL

SPOKE N 3 – CULTURAL-INDUSTRY REGENERATION IMMERSIVE LAB

DELIVERABLE D 4: SHERIL Pilot

REPORTING PERIOD	
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Milestone 8.1 Responsible	Prof. Paolo Esposito
RM8 Responsible	Prof. Paolo Esposito

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Glossary

	Definition
Hub Coordinator (HC)	The Hub Coordinator represents the single point of contact for the implementation of the innovation ecosystem towards the MUR. It carries out the management and coordination activities of the innovation ecosystem, receives the fundings, verifies, and transmits to the MUR the reporting of the activities carried out by the Spoke and their affiliates.
National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP)	This document uses the Italian acronym for the NRRP, which is PNRR (Piano Nazionale della Ripresa e Resilienza)
Research Program Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the NODES project. The NODES will appoint the Research Program Manager. It refers to "Responsabile del Programma di Ricerca" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione"
NODES' Research and innovation program	NODES' Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spoke, with the aim to promote and support applied research on topics consistent with the Intelligent Specialization Strategy, with the guidelines of the 2021-2027 partnership agreement scheme, with regional operational plans and regional and national research and innovation priorities. Although NODES' Spokes are concentrated on different themes, they will organize their activities and actions within a common framework – NODES' Booster Methodology
Spoke Coordinator	The University in charge of coordinating the Spoke's ecosystem. It refers to "Spoke" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione"
Spoke Data Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the monitoring and management of data generated at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Data Manager.
Spoke Partner	The entity associated to the Spoke Coordinator. It can be an Innovation Cluster, Competence Center, Research Center related to the Spoke's ecosystem and contributes to achieve objectives and impact under the Spoke' leadership and management. It refers to "soggetti affiliati" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione".
Spoke Project manager	The person who will be the responsible for the management, coordination and progress of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Project Manager.
Spoke research and innovation program	NODES' Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spokes. The spoke will leverage a consolidated collaboration with leading private and public companies and will focus the applied research activity on technological domains and applications that can favour the integration of SMEs into new value chains.
Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager.
Spoke Stakeholders Committee (SC)	Consultation structure formed by relevant stakeholders (Government, universities, companies, civil society, third sector, etc.)
Spoke Thematic	General target focus and domain of the Spoke research.
Spoke Topics	Specific areas/lines of development within the Spoke.
Spoke Work Package Leader	At the Spoke level, Work Packages (WPs) will be organized by WP leaders, who will be responsible for performance evaluation and reporting.
Flagship Project	Main research project at the Spoke level with the goal of prototyping, testing, demonstrating the research activities towards higher TRLs.

List of Deliverables

#	Name	Type		Due month	Due date	Short description	New Due Date (if delay)	Delivery Date (actual)
D1	Context related analysis of lesser known cultural areas	R	PU	12	30/03/2024			03/04/2024
D2	Technological mock-up for personalised itineraries	R	PU	18	30/09/2024			30/09/2024
D3	Methodology and training contents based on immersive technologies approach	R	PU	24	30/04/2025			30/04/2025
D4	SHERIL Pilot	DEM	PU	38	30/09/2025			22/12/2025

List of Milestone

#	Name	Type	Due month	Due date	Short description	New Due Date (if delay)	Delivery Date (actual)
M1	Analysis of the state of art and Point of Interests (POI)	R	10	04/02/2024	.		04/04/2024
M2	Main user domain and user content defined		14	18/03/2024			18/03/2024

A) EXPLANATION OF THE WORK CARRIED OUT AND OVERVIEW OF THE PROGRESS

1. Introduction

1.1 Objective of the Deliverable

Deliverable D4 entitled "SHERIL Pilot" is the last deliverable and it is started in March 2025, at the achievement of the D3 named "Methodology and training contents based on immersive technologies approach".

All Milestones have been already reached.

1.2 Context

The Research Team is composed by Professor Gerardo Canfora, Rector of University del Sannio, Gaetano Natullo, Director of Department of Law, Economics, Management and Quantitative Methods (DEMM), Paolo Esposito, Angelo Riviezzo, Daniele Davino, Antonella Tartaglia Polcini, Guido Migliaccio and Giudo Tortorella Esposito.

Other three Member of the Research Team are: Piera Zerillo, Research Fellow, Vitiana L'Abate, Post-Doc Research Fellow till 30/06/2025, and Massimiliano Tufo, Ph.D. Student.

2. Literature Background

2.1. Public Value in Museums

The concept of public value, as articulated in Moore's (1995) strategic triangle, emphasizes the need to align the authorising environment, operational and administrative capacities, and an organisation's mission, in order to create value for the public (Virtanen & Jalonen, 2024). In this framework, public value is understood as "the value created by government through services, laws regulation and other actions" (Kelly et al., 2002; p. 4). Stoker adds further depth by arguing that public value is "more than a summation of individual preferences of the users or producers of public services ... [it] is collectively built through deliberation involving elected and appointed government officials and key stakeholders" (2006; p. 42). These definitions highlight that public value is a multidimensional and evolving concept, realised through the shared purpose and operational capacity of public institutions.

In the context of cultural organizations, this conceptualization has catalyzed extensive scholarly inquiry into the nature and measurement of the public value these institutions generate for society. Museums are increasingly viewed as active agents of public value, encompassing educational provision, social cohesion, community identity formation, and wellbeing enhancement, alongside fiduciary responsibility to funders and the broader public (Scott, 2010a; Yocco et al., 2009; Meyrick & Barnett, 2021; Righettini & Ibba, 2022).

Scott (2006) distinguishes three primary dimensions of museum-generated value: individual, societal, and economic. Individual value refers to the benefits directly experienced by visitors, such as personal enrichment and learning. Societal value

encompasses contributions to the social and cultural fabric, including civic engagement, identity reinforcement, and cultural continuity. Economic value refers to the institution's tangible and intangible impacts on local and regional economies, including employment, tourism, and multiplier effects. Building on Scott's (2006) tripartite model, Yocco et al. (2009) operationalize individual, social, and economic factors for measuring public value within the museum sector, thereby bridging theory and practice.

The application of public value theory requires cultural organizations to maintain strategic congruence with stakeholder expectations. Weinberg and Lewis (2009) argue that a museum's legitimacy and societal endorsement are contingent upon its mission's alignment with community values; divergence risks erosion of public trust and relevance. Further emphasizing stakeholder heterogeneity, Goodwin and Pekarek (2025) demonstrate that diverse groups prioritize different value indicators, ranging from curatorial and collection excellence to interpersonal experiences and accessibility. This influences stakeholder engagement during the disclosure of corporate social responsibility (Esposito & Ricci, 2021).

Empirical research substantiates the cross-national applicability and utility of the public value framework. In Turkey, Herguner (2015) documents how public value facilitates a balance between managerial efficiency and preservation of cultural missions. Grüb and Martin (2020) report that Austrian citizens perceive cultural organizations primarily as generators of collective societal value, underscoring the civic dimension of public perception. In Sweden, Thomson and Caicedo (2014) illustrate the role of public value in guiding museum policy and management through periods of institutional transition. Extending the conceptual boundaries, Scott (2008) introduced the categories of existence, option, and bequest values to capture non-use and intergenerational benefits, elements often overlooked in conventional evaluative paradigms.

Digital transformation has emerged as a strategic enabler for enhancing the public value of museums. Grcheva and Oktay Vehbi (2021) observe that digital technologies expand access, foster engagement, and enhance transparency and accountability. Righettini and Ibba (2022) present a case study of the Uffizi Galleries during the COVID-19 pandemic, illustrating how digital platforms facilitated public interaction and cultural participation under conditions of physical closure, thereby reinforcing museums' civic functions.

Crucially, Ebbers et al. (2021) highlight the benefits of meaningful stakeholder involvement in decision-making processes, which contribute to institutional legitimacy and responsiveness. Nonetheless, Najda-Janoszka and Sawczuk (2023) identify significant organizational and cultural barriers that limit participatory potential, including entrenched hierarchical structures, weak mechanisms for stakeholder identification, and constrained scopes for co-creation. Case studies reviewed by Kershaw et al. (2020) underscore that collaborative museum-community practices generate both symbolic and functional value, thereby reinforcing museums' role as vital civic institutions embedded within broader public ecosystems. In conclusion, public value in museums is a dynamic and contested phenomenon, continually negotiated among diverse actors and subject to evolving societal conditions.

2.2. Sustainable tourism and public value

Public museums stand at the intersection of cultural mission and institutional obligation, yet they are increasingly required to implement sustainable tourism policies and practices that extend beyond heritage conservation to encompass technological innovation, public participation, and economic sustainability. Christensen and Mohr (2003) demonstrate that museum annual reports often fail to capture the full extent of institutional impact, limiting communication to financial compliance. Ellwood and Greenwood (2016) argue that assigning economic value to heritage assets may obscure their cultural and symbolic significance, advocating for valuation approaches that reflect the diverse interests of stakeholders. Esposito et al. (2021), analyzing Italian virtual museums, describe how digital accounting environments support new governance forms based on stakeholder engagement and emotional connection, particularly under resource constraints. Isaksson and Garvare (2003) conceptualize it as a balance among economic prosperity, environmental protection, and social equity.

However, as Jamroz (2007) notes, many sustainable tourism strategies remain oriented toward consumer demand rather than societal outcomes, raising questions about long-term alignment with public value objectives. Cultural organizations, situated within this landscape, are expected to contribute to local development while maintaining their cultural mission. Economic valuation studies, such as Tohmo (2004), demonstrate that museums contribute to regional economies not only through direct revenue but also through their perceived social value, as captured by willingness-to-pay analyses.

Drawing on the literature review, public value is a multifaceted integration of economic, social, and environmental dimensions, which can be created or destroyed for stakeholders. Starting from the pyramidal structure proposed by Gagliardo et al. (2025), Figure 1 depicts the developed theoretical framework.

Figure 1: Public Value theoretical framework.

Source: Authors' elaboration.

3. Research context

This study focuses on a context characterized by a global market related to museums, historical sites, zoos, and parks. This ecosystem encompasses a wide range of services, including ticketing, membership, retail, food services, events, educational and digital

services, whose overall valuation (estimated between USD 91.4 and 103.6 billion depending on the methodologies adopted) is supported by the recovery of tourist flows, the proliferation of immersive experiences, and the integration of digital solutions. The analysis of pre- and post-pandemic trends reveals a marked contraction during the 2020–2021 biennium, followed by a gradual recovery over the 2022–2024 triennium, with reported values of USD 56.6 billion in 2022 and USD 58.2 billion in 2023 (UNWTO, 2024).

From a geographical perspective, 2024 highlights the leadership of North America, which accounts for approximately 36% of the global market value, followed by Europe and rapidly expanding Asia (The Business Research Company, 2025). This distribution reflects differentiated funding models: a greater reliance on public support in Europe and a significant role for philanthropy and sponsorships in the United States. The concentration of demand in major cultural hubs is evidenced by visitor volumes at leading international institutions, reaffirming the centrality of Europe and the USA as museum hubs, alongside the progressive strengthening of Asia.

The Italian context shows clear signs of post-pandemic recovery, with increased revenues and attendance in 2024 compared to 2023, driven by ticketing, ancillary services, and a return to pre-pandemic levels. This recovery is supported by a mix of public and private funding aimed at innovating temporary and digital experiences. Between 2011 and 2019, profits from cultural organizations, monuments, archaeological areas, and museum in Italy rose from approximately EUR 117 million to EUR 242 million. In 2021, profits increased from approximately EUR 53 million in 2020 to EUR 89 million, representing a growth rate of 68% (The Business Research Company, 2025). In 2024, ticket revenues increased and now represent 34% of total revenue, compared to 33% in 2023 (Osservatorio Innovazione Digitale nei Beni Culturali, 2025). In 2021, the Lazio region recorded the highest number of museum visitors, accounting for approximately 32.1% of the national total, followed by Campania with 24.9% and Tuscany with 15.7%. Digital services remain a structural challenge: only 41% of the sample offers audio guides, of which 71% are free or included in the ticket price, while 29% require an additional fee (Osservatorio Innovazione Digitale nei Beni Culturali, 2025). Only 31% provide a mobile app, and for 92% of these, the app is free or included in the ticket price; the remaining 8% require separate payment. Virtual Reality (VR) or Augmented Reality (AR) experiences are available in only 20% of cases and are mostly free or included in the ticket price. In fact, the empirical application of the study focuses on Italian cultural organizations because of Italy's exceptionally dense cultural heritage. Italy ranks as the country with the highest number of UNESCO World Heritage properties, precisely 61 (UNESCO, 2025), and hosts more than 4.500 museums, archaeological sites, monuments and similar cultural institutions (ISTAT, 2024).

4. Methodology

This study adopts UNESCO's Framework for Cultural Statistics (2009, p. 29; 2025, p. 7) and operationalizes it in the Cultural Heritage sector. The nature of this research is both qualitative (Baskarada, 2014; Flick, 2022) and quantitative (Langfield-Smith, 2006; Ghanad, 2023).

For the first phase, the multiple case-study method was employed to examine how and why specific phenomena recur within particular contexts, thereby enabling the contextualization of general models within site-specific settings (Stake, 2013; Yin, 2009)

and addressing the need for theory development oriented to practice (Edmondson & McManus, 2007).

For the second phase, a quantitative analysis of audited financial statements was conducted for the period 2019–2024, during which a set of key economic and financial metrics (e.g., revenues, EBITDA, EBITDA margin, net financial position, and equity) was extracted and standardized for cross-case comparison and econometric assessment.

4.1. Multiple case-studies selection

The authors developed the analysis in a single country (i.e., Italy) to avoid the results being influenced by the political, cultural, and regulatory differences existing in different countries. They did not select the cases to highlight the impact of national contexts, but rather due to their similarity and rarity. The decision to analyse multiple case studies enhances data reliability and observational rigour (South et al., 2024). Moreover, a comparative analysis yields a broader understanding of the investigated problem, thereby enabling the identification of a greater range of potential solutions. Both in the private and in the public sector, multiple case-studies methodology “is shaped by both by the research design (that is, the relationship between objective and method) and by the doing of the research” (Stewart, 2012: p. 73). The multiple case studies are selected from different geographical areas of Italy to better represent the analysis and are presented below.

4.2. Data collection

In line with the observations of Yin (2009) and Stake (2013), a mixed-methodological approach was employed in this study. In this regard, data were collected through both primary and secondary sources. The primary advantage is the development of convergence among lines of inquiry, specifically a process of triangulation (Yin, 2003). The results obtained through the multiple case studies methodology are more convincing and accurate if based on different sources of information, following the method of mutual confirmation.

4.3. Validity and reliability of data

The data were initially aggregated and subsequently subjected to triangulation. Specifically, the triangulation technique enables the attribution of greater credibility, accuracy, and validity to the results of qualitative research (Bans-Akutey & Tiimub, 2021). In fact, analysing multiple sources makes it possible to measure the same phenomenon in different ways, thereby increasing the value of the results obtained. Indeed, in qualitative research, triangulation represents the equivalent of the reliability tests performed in quantitative research (Creswell, J. W., & Creswell, J. D., 2017; Ricciardelli et al., 2020). In order to correctly conduct a case study, Patton (2014) has identified four types of triangulation. More specifically, these four typologies concern the triangulation of data sources, methods, and perspectives on the same dataset and between different evaluators. For the purposes of this study, triangulation of data sources and methods was performed. First, multiple data sources were cross-referenced, including direct observations and a review

of documents and digital information provided on the museum's website and social media platforms. This approach allowed for a thorough comparison of data, facilitating a comprehensive understanding of the phenomenon and enhancing the reliability and credibility of the findings from diverse sources. Second, methodological triangulation, which combines various data collection techniques, was employed to mitigate the limitations inherent in individual methods and ensure a more refined dataset. This dual approach contributed to a well-rounded and robust analysis of the multiple case studies.

4.4. Data analysis

Data analysis enables researchers to capture and understand the true meaning of the information collected (Creswell & Poth, 2016). Since the data collected are of a qualitative nature, it is necessary to adopt an approach that considers the "Grounded Theory" (Charmaz, 2006). This theory enables the identification of key points that will later be transformed into codes (Bryant & Charmaz, 2011). Subsequently, it is necessary to collect the selected codes in order to identify the concepts that make the data usable. Finally, starting from the concepts, it is necessary to form categories for fundamentals to formulate and discuss the results.

This approach was implemented based on previous studies on the subject (Strauss & Corbin, 1998; Yin, 2009). At the end of this process, the data analysis was divided into three phases: cross-analysis of the raw data, extrapolation of themes from the raw data and interpretation of the data. The first phase involved analysing the raw data to understand and evaluate the phenomenon. In this way, preliminary conclusions were obtained, which led to the exclusion of unnecessary data to answer the research questions. The second phase involved encoding the data through identification, naming, extrapolation and finally classification. In this regard, the data has been classified according to the source. Finally, the third phase involved interpreting the data to assess their relevance to the objectives of this analysis.

5. Results

5.1. Città della Scienza (Napoli)

"Città della Scienza", managed by the "Fondazione IDIS – Città della Scienza", is a major science promotion and dissemination complex located in the Bagnoli district of Naples. The first opened exhibition spaces in 1996; the Foundation, established in 1987 as a non-profit entity, is committed to the diffusion of scientific culture, public engagement with science, open collaboration and the cross-fertilization of competences across sectors. The site is organised as a multifunctional centre that integrates an interactive Science Centre, advanced training facilities, a Business Innovation Centre (BIC), and convention and events spaces. The Science Centre, acknowledged as Italy's first interactive science museum, is designed as a locus of experimentation, informal learning, and dialogic engagement with science and technology. Its pedagogical approach privileges hands-on interactivity and direct experimentation with natural phenomena and technological systems, thereby facilitating experiential learning across age groups. Within the complex, Corporea is structured around thematic islands that focus on different bodily systems,

offering numerous hands-on exhibits, open laboratories, and researcher-led activities that enable visitors to investigate health-related phenomena and biomedical technologies. The Planetario 3D operates as a three-dimensional sky simulator, supporting astronomy outreach through scientific shows and curriculum-related programming in astrophysics and space technology. The D.RE.A.M. FabLab functions as a fabrication laboratory devoted to research, experimentation and technical training in digital manufacturing and maker-oriented practices, while the Business Innovation Centre provides incubation services and specialised facilities aimed at supporting the development and scaling of new projects and enterprises. The on-site congress centre hosts conferences, professional events, and large-scale public programming.

5.2. Galileo Museum (Firenze)

The “Museo Galileo” (Istituto e Museo di Storia della Scienza) is a specialised research and exhibition institution that holds one of the world’s most important collections of scientific instruments, historic telescopes and archive material illustrating the development of early modern science. Established from the institutional legacy of the Istituto e Museo di Storia della Scienza, the museum is located in Palazzo Castellani and is both a centre for scholarly research in the history of science and an active public museum. Its permanent collection comprises over one thousand instruments and an extensive documentary and library corpus, while its educational remit includes a prolific programme of didactic activities, workshops and public events. In 2024, the museum reported visitor and participation figures that underscore its strong national and international profile. The Museo Galileo’s curatorial practice foregrounds object-based scholarship, conservation-led display, and didactic mediation. The institution increasingly pursues digital dissemination and international research collaborations, positioning itself as a node between academic research, heritage stewardship, and public outreach.

5.3. Leonardo Da Vinci Museum (Milano)

The Museo Nazionale della Scienza e della Tecnologia “Leonardo da Vinci” is Italy’s largest cultural organization devoted to the history of science and technology, and one of the principal technical and scientific museums in Europe. Housed in the historic complex of San Vittore al Corpo, the institution occupies an exhibition footprint of approximately 50,000 m² and combines extensive historical collections with interactive learning environments and specialised laboratories. The museum’s permanent holdings encompass a broad spectrum of domains (from transport and energy to telecommunications, space and particle physics) and include the world’s most significant assemblage of historic models inspired by Leonardo da Vinci’s drawings. Its research and educational infrastructure comprises a large library and archives, a centre for informal learning (CREI), and a portfolio of laboratories and outreach programmes oriented towards schools, families, and specialist audiences. In recent years, the cultural organization has consolidated a hybrid mission that combines conservation and scholarship with experiential public engagement, museum-led research, and industry partnerships. Its operational model relies on a mixed funding base, including institutional support, project-based income, ticketing, and commercial activities, thereby enabling sizable year-on-year programming and capital maintenance.

5.4. MUSE (Trento)

“Museo delle Scienze” (MUSE) is a science and natural history museum conceived as a research-oriented public institution, with a distributed territorial system of sites throughout the Trentino region. Opened in its present Renzo Piano-designed headquarters in 2013, MUSE integrates research departments, laboratories, didactic activities, and extensive exhibition spaces that emphasise ecology, biodiversity, and the human-environment interface, with a specific focus on mountain ecosystems and Alpine research. The cultural organization operates as a “museum laboratory” model that links scientific research, environmental monitoring and educational programming, and it manages a network of territorial sites, field stations and outreach initiatives across the province. Operationally, MUSE combines public funding, project revenue and philanthropic support to sustain research projects, temporary exhibitions and long-term educational outreach. In 2024, the MUSE system recorded consolidated visit volumes in the mid-hundreds of thousands, reflecting both local engagement and national tourism flows. Under its current strategic orientation, the institution prioritises research integration, territorial impact and inclusive access, while expanding collaborations with universities, research centres and international partners to amplify its role as a platform for science communication and sustainability education.

5.5. Museo del Sannio

The Sannio Museum, located in the historic center of Benevento, serves as a key institution for the study and enhancement of the cultural heritage of the ancient Samnite territory. Established in 1873, during a period marked by a growing interest in local historical identity, the museum has progressively assumed a central role in the preservation of the archaeological and artistic-historical legacy of the province. Since 1929, it has been housed within the cloister and premises of the monastic complex of Santa Sofia, one of the most emblematic sites in Lombard Benevento, which was included in the UNESCO World Heritage List in 2011. The exhibition path is structured in several sections and includes artefacts that document the culture of the Samnites, the process of Romanization in the area, the significance of the Lombard Duchy of Benevento, and artistic expressions from the Middle Ages to the modern era. The museum also hosts a substantial numismatic collection, a bibliographic section, and offers educational activities involving schools and the local community. Through its curatorial and outreach functions, the museum not only safeguards and interprets the past but also plays an active role in creating public value in the cultural domain at the local level.

5.6. S'ADIM Museum

The “Complesso Sant’Agostino” in Benevento, originally founded in the 13th century in the Trescene district near the city walls, has played a significant role in the city's religious and social history. Initially home to Augustinian monks, the complex was an important center of theological and philosophical study during the Middle Ages. Severely damaged by the 1688 earthquake, it was rebuilt with a Baroque appearance, incorporating elaborate

stucco decorations and frescoes that still bear witness to its artistic significance. After its closure as a convent in 1861 and as a church in 1865, the site was repurposed as a military barracks, reflecting the broader secularization policies of the post-unification period. It later hosted the Parish of Sant'Agostino before undergoing further transformations. Today, the "Complesso Sant'Agostino" serves as the headquarters of the engineering department of the University of Sannio, housing classrooms, study areas, computer labs, and administrative offices. Beyond the central cloister, which remains independently accessible from the exterior, lies the Church of Sant'Agostino, repurposed as both an auditorium and a lecture hall. The complex also features extensive gardens and the Oratory of Sant'Antonio, renowned for its frescoed walls and partially preserved stucco decorations. Despite its architectural and historical significance, the site remains relatively unknown to the general public, although recent digitalization and conservation initiatives have sought to enhance its visibility and accessibility.

5.7. SHERIL (Samnium Heritage Innovation Lab)

SHERIL (Samnium Heritage Innovation Lab) is a service center of the University of Sannio that carries out research, technology transfer, advanced training, and support for business creation in the field of knowledge, protection, and enhancement of tangible and intangible cultural heritage. Its mission is pursued through a multidisciplinary approach that fosters close interconnections between STEM disciplines and the humanities.

The center is committed to developing advanced solutions for the conservation of cultural assets, designing digital and immersive experiences of cultural engagement, promoting innovative models of the cultural economy, and training highly specialized professional profiles. Particular emphasis is placed on research aimed at enhancing access to cultural heritage, through the design of tools and pathways to accompany the experience of tangible and intangible assets, the safeguarding of archaeological resources and green ecosystems, as well as the economic and social development of the territory, with culture positioned as a driver of sustainable growth.

The project is grounded in a strong institutional and entrepreneurial partnership that includes local public authorities, cultural institutions, all major universities in Campania, and companies specializing in digitization and gaming, diagnostics and restoration, as well as IoT and ICT technologies. The center focuses especially on key research areas such as art, biodiversity, digitization, conservation, and the promotion of the creative industries, all addressed through a multidisciplinary and innovation-oriented perspective.

SHERIL is equipped with highly specialized laboratories, training facilities, and interactive exhibition spaces, including an immersive room for the digital enjoyment of cultural heritage and soundscapes. The infrastructure also comprises monitoring systems, data centers, augmented and virtual reality technologies, and environments dedicated to the incubation of cultural enterprises and spin-offs. Through SHERIL, the University of Sannio strengthens its commitment to integrating innovation and culture, technology and territorial identity, advanced research and social impact, thereby promoting a vision of culture as a strategic lever for sustainable and inclusive development in Southern Italy.

On June 13, 2025, the Board of Directors and the Academic Senate of the University of Sannio formally approved the establishment of SHERIL – Samnium Heritage Innovation

Lab.

6. Conclusion

The comparative analysis of Italian cultural institutions reveals a clear convergence toward hybrid organizational models that integrate conservation, research, and experiential public engagement. Large museums with extensive infrastructures, demonstrate the advantages of diversified funding, research integration, and territorial networks. Specialized institutions, exemplify object-centered scholarship, immersive pedagogy, and effective digital dissemination. Local anchors like the Museo del Sannio and the S'ADIM show substantial untapped potential for cultural value creation through increased visibility, targeted digitization, and community-centered programming. Within this landscape, SHerIL is well positioned to act as an integrative platform that connects STEM and the humanities, catalyzes regional partnerships, and advances sustainable cultural development across Samnium.

SHerIL embodies the ethos of the New European Bauhaus, reframing technological, environmental, and digital transformations to valorize our artistic and cultural heritage, thereby catalyzing new services and fostering a next-generation cultural industry. SHerIL consolidate its role as a regional coordinator of shared infrastructures (extended reality environments, data centers, and monitoring systems) while co-developing research-based public programs with museums, universities, and local authorities. Establishing a deliberate cross-disciplinary framework that combines conservation science, digital humanities, archaeology, bioacoustics, and data-driven curation differentiate outputs and accelerate translation into public value. By orienting activity toward territorial impact (green heritage monitoring, inclusive access initiatives, and entrepreneurship in the creative industries) SHerIL can position culture as a driver of sustainable growth and social cohesion. A distinct identity that is Samnium-centered, innovation-led, and internationally connected strengthen visibility, attract talent and partners, and enhance funding capacity.

An immersive program focused on Benevento and Samnium heritage (combining on-site AR, remote VR, and curated soundscapes) expand access, align with educational curricula, and elevate international profile. A Conservation and Biodiversity Lab integrating heritage diagnostics with environmental monitoring (IoT sensors, bioacoustic surveys, climate risk analysis) would generate novel research outputs at the culture–nature nexus and inform evidence-based stewardship. Systematic digitization of the Museo del Sannio's collections, coupled with interoperable datasets and open APIs, would enable scholarly collaboration, enhance accessibility, and provide a foundation for narrative-driven public interpretation. A targeted accelerator for culture-tech ventures in digitization, gaming, and heritage applications would stimulate new enterprises, skilled employment, and a sustained innovation pipeline.

5. Contribution of the Deliverable to NODES Objectives

Findings of the analysis, regarding public value creation and public value destruction, are part of 13 papers published in International Scientific Journals or Conference Proceedings.

Moreover, 3 papers are submitted in two International Scientific Journals and one Conference.

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7. Publications during NODES' research project

1. Esposito, P., Doronzo, E., Tufo, M., & Riso, V. (2025). Unveiling the relationship between cultural values and public (dis)value: the mediation role of corruption perception and citizen trust. *Corporate Social Responsibility and Environmental Management*, 32 (4), 4462-4481. Wiley Online Library, New York, USA. ISSN:1535-3966, Print ISSN:1535-3958. <https://doi.org/10.1002/csr.3192> [Rivista di Classe A ANVUR/ASN (Q1 e ABS1)].
2. Esposito, P., Tallaki, M., & Tufo, M. (2025). Dissecting the destruction of Public Value in Public-Private Partnerships (PPPs). In Bracci et al. (eds.), *Public Value Accounting: Current and Future Issues* (pp. 173-192). Emerald Studies in Public Service Accounting and Accountability. Emerald Publishing Group, Leeds, UK. ISBN: 978-1-83797-536-5 (electronic) <https://doi.org/10.1108/978-1-83797-536-520251012>
3. Tufo, M., & Esposito, P. (2025). Innovation Meets Tradition: Integrating Immersive Technologies for a Sustainable Future in Cultural Heritage. In Vrontis et al. (eds.), *Business in a Turbulent Era, Volume I: Organisations, Industries and Markets* (pp. 293-313). Palgrave Macmillan, Cham: Springer Nature Switzerland. Print ISBN: 978-3-031-89797-9, Online ISBN: 978-3-031-89798-6. ISSN 2523-8167, ISSN 2523-8175 (electronic) https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-89798-6_13 Scopus-listed Book Series "Palgrave Studies in Cross-disciplinary Business Research, In Association with EuroMed Academy of Business".
4. Esposito, P., & Tufo, M. (2025). Understanding False Accounting Practices in Nonprofit Organizations: Prevention and Detection. In Vrontis D. et al., *Exploring New Horizons in Business and Management* (p. 1037). 18th Annual Conference of the EuroMed Academy of Business, Euromed Press, Cyprus. ISSN: 2547-8516, ISBN: 978-9925-628-05-6.
5. Esposito, P., & Tufo, M. (2025). Public Value Creation in Sustainable Tourism: Multiple Case Studies of Cultural Organisations. In Vrontis D. et al., *Exploring New Horizons in Business and Management* (p. 1040). 18th Annual Conference of the EuroMed

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6. Esposito, P., & Tufo, M., (2025). Public Value Creation through the Digitalization of cultural heritage: insights from a Historic Italian site. EGPA (European Group for Public Administration) 2025 Conference, University of Glasgow, Glasgow, Scotland, UK, 26th - 29th August 2025.
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 8. Esposito P., & L'Abate, V. (2025). Digitalization of Cultural Heritage in Service of the SDGs and Public Value: A Case Study from Southern Italy, AFLUM Conference 2025, Università LUM "Giuseppe Degennaro", Bari 9 - 10 June 2025.
 9. Dicorato, S. L., & Tufo, M. (2025). Forensic Accounting in action: uncovering Mafia Infiltration and the Public Disvalue in Municipalities. SIDREA International Workshop (SIW) "Public (dis)value accounting and accountability: a stakeholder theory perspective". University of Naples "Parthenope", Villa Doria D'Angri, Naples, Italy, 26 Maggio 2025.
 10. L'Abate, V., & Tufo, M. (2025). Museum Digitization and Public Value: a Stakeholder-Centered perspective across Economic, Social, and Environmental Dimensions. SIDREA International Workshop (SIW) "Public (dis)value accounting and accountability: a stakeholder theory perspective". University of Naples "Parthenope", Villa Doria D'Angri, Naples, Italy, 26 Maggio 2025.
 11. Esposito P., Tufo, M., Rossi, P., & Boggio, G. (2024). From bytes to beauty: ICT's influence on cultural heritage valorization. In Vrontis D. et al., *Global Business Transformation in a Turbulent Era* (p. 810). 17th Annual Conference of the EuroMed Academy of Business, Euromed Press, Cyprus. ISSN: 2547-8516, ISBN: 978-9925-628-01-8.
 12. Esposito, P., Tufo, M., Rossi, P., & Boggio, G. (2024). Culture-driven Urban Regeneration: transforming cities through creativity and technology. In Vrontis D. et al., *Global Business Transformation in a Turbulent Era* (p. 811). 17th Annual Conference of the EuroMed Academy of Business, Euromed Press, Cyprus. ISSN: 2547-8516, ISBN: 978-9925-628-01-8.
 13. Esposito P., Tufo M., Rossi P., & Boggio G. (2024). Retracing public value creation through digital and sustainable transformation. A Recovery Plan case study. EGPA

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8. Paper Under Review

1. Esposito P., & Tufo M. (2025). Measuring Public Value through the lens of Triple Bottom Line for sustainable tourism. *Management Decision*. [submitted 30 September 2025]
2. Esposito P., & Tufo M. (2025). Pixels and Patrons: Reimagining Cultural Organizations across Economic, Social, and Environmental Dimensions. International Workshop "Crafting Qualitative Research in Management & Accounting", University of Naples "Parthenope", 5-6 November 2025. [submitted 30 September 2025]
3. Esposito P., & L'Abate, V. (2025). Digitalization of Cultural Heritage in Service of the SDGs and Public Value: A Case Study from Southern Italy. *Journal of Management and Governance*. [submitted 25 April 2025]
4. Esposito P., Riviezzo A., Coppola D., & Tufo M. (2025). Musei Pubblici e Musei Privati d'impresa: Digitalizzazione, Identità Aziendale e nuove Narrazioni Culturali. Convegno Department of Law, Economics, Management and Quantitative Methods (DEMM) "Transizione digitale e ambientale". University of Sannio [submitted 27 September 2025]